

Supporting Information

Spin-dependent electron transfer in electrochemically transparent van der Waals heterostructure for oxygen evolution reaction

Yang Li^{a,b,*}, Yan Wang^a, Andrew F. May^c, Mauro Fianchini^{d,e}, Chiara Biz^d, Saeyoung Oh^f, Yiru Zhu^a, Hu Young Jeong^f, Jieun Yang^g, Jose Gracia^d, Manish Chhowalla^{a,**}

*Corresponding author. Email address: yl539@cam.ac.

**Corresponding author. Email address: mc209@cam.ac.uk.

Figure S1. Energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) for elemental mapping in encapsulated Fe_3GeTe_2 (FGT) flake. Scale bar, 1 nm. (a) Fe. (b) Ge. (c) Te.

Figure S2. Temperature dependence of longitudinal resistance (R_{xx}) of encapsulated FGT. R_{xx} increases monotonically with increasing temperature, indicating metallic behavior.

Figure S3. Raman spectra at room temperature for FGT exposed in air and encapsulated by graphene and hBN. A peak at 155 cm^{-1} was observed in all FGT samples, which can be attributed to the $A_{1g}(\Gamma)$ and $E_{2g}(\Gamma)$ modes of FGT [1]. When FGT was exposed to air, a new peak at 124 cm^{-1} appeared immediately due to degradation of the sample [1].

Figure S4. (a) Optical image of graphene microelectrochemical cell. Scale bar, $10\text{ }\mu\text{m}$. (b) Polarization curves (10 mV s^{-1}) in 1 M KOH ($\text{pH} \approx 14$) for graphene microelectrochemical cell at two different spin polarization states.

Figure S5. Raman spectra of top layer graphene in graphene/FGT heterostructure as catalysts before and after OER measurements.

Figure S6. Electrochemical performance in 1 M KOH ($\text{pH} \approx 14$) for graphene/FGT heterostructures with different thickness of graphene as labelled at two different spin polarization states.

Figure S7. Electron tunnelling effect in FGT/hBN/FGT heterostructures. (a) Optical image of FGT/hBN/FGT device with bottom Au electrodes. Scale bar, 10 μm . (b)-(f) I - V_b curves measured at different temperatures with different thickness of hBN.

Figure S8. Magnetoresistance of FGT/hBN/FGT tunnel junction with $I = 200 \text{ nA}$ at 10.6 K.

Figure S9. (a) Optical image of hBN microelectrochemical cell. Scale bar, 10 μm . (b) Polarization curves (10 mV s^{-1}) in 1 M KOH ($\text{pH} \approx 14$) for hBN microelectrochemical cell at two different spin polarization states.

Figure S10. Raman spectra of top layer hBN in hBN/FGT heterostructure as catalysts before and after OER measurements.

Figure S11. Electrochemical performance in 1 M KOH (pH \approx 14) for hBN/FGT heterostructures with different thickness of hBN as labelled at two different spin polarization states.

Figure S12. Structure characterization of Fe₅GeTe₂ (FGT5). (a) Schematic crystal structure of FGT5. The dashed box denotes the crystal unit cell with $a = 4.04 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 29.19 \text{ \AA}$. The structure of FGT5 is similar to FGT but with three different Fe sites. (b) Field cooling magnetization as a function of the temperature for FGT5 bulk crystals in a field ($\mu_0 H_{\text{app}} = 0.1 \text{ T}$) perpendicular to the c -axis. The ferromagnetic phase in FGT5 can stay up to room temperature ($T_c = 296 \text{ K}$).

Figure S13. Electrochemical performance in 1 M KOH (pH ≈ 14) for graphene/FGT5 heterostructures with different thickness of graphene as labelled at two different spin polarization states.

Figure S14. Electrochemical performance in 1 M KOH ($\text{pH} \approx 14$) for $\text{MoS}_2/\text{FGT5}$ heterostructures with different thickness of MoS_2 as labelled at two different spin polarization states.

Figure S15. Electrochemical performance in 1 M KOH (pH ≈ 14) for hBN/FGT5 heterostructures with different thickness of hBN as labelled at two different spin polarization states.

Figure S16. Comparison of the OER enhancement between bulk materials and van der Waals heterostructure as spin catalysts. OER enhancement is defined as the percentage change in current density during the OER relative to the current density in its pristine state. Magnetic oxides and Raney Ni catalysts data are from Refs. [2,3].

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